

Cross-cultural adaptation and validation of the Norwegian Short-form McGill Pain Questionnaire-2 in low back-related leg pain

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Introduction

The McGill Pain Questionnaire has been an important and influential tool for pain assessment since it first was developed in the mid 1970s^{1,2}. To provide a more efficient alternative to the original questionnaire, the Short-Form McGill Pain Questionnaire (SF-MPQ) was developed a decade later³. The SF-MPQ included 15 descriptors (11 sensory and 4 affective) scored as none, mild, moderate or severe; a visual analogue scale with endpoints no pain and worst possible pain; and a verbal scale for pain using the words no pain, mild, discomforting, distressing, horrible or excruciating. Since the development of the SF-MPQ there has been increasing interest in the assessment of neuropathic pain mechanisms and characteristics, and the descriptors included in the SF-MPQ for assessing this dimension were found inadequate. A revised version—SF-MPQ-2—was developed to more reliably assess the qualities of both neuropathic and non-neuropathic pain⁴. The SF-MPQ-2 includes seven additional descriptors to cover pain-qualities or symptoms relevant to neuropathic pain. A 0–10 numeric rating scale for each descriptor replaces the earlier verbal ratings, and the visual analogue scale and verbal scale for pain is removed. Further, the 22 pain descriptors in total are now divided into four subscales consisting of three sensory; continuous, intermittent and neuropathic; and one affective.

All versions of the questionnaire have had reliability and validity assessment⁵⁻⁷. Both the long and the first short-form have been adapted in Norwegian^{8,9}, however no translation of the SF-MPQ-2 have been performed. The aim of the present study was therefore to translate the SF-MPQ-2 into Norwegian, and to assess its internal consistency reliability and its validity in a patient population with low back-related leg pain.

Materials and methods

Study design

A prospective observational study with translation, cross-cultural adaptation, and psychometric analyses. The study was approved by the Norwegian Regional Committee for Medical Research Ethics.

Setting

Patients included in the present study took part in a prospective, 1-year observational study on prognostic factors in patients with low back-related leg pain referred to a secondary health-care back clinic at the Østfold Hospital Trust, Norway.

Patient population

Inclusion criteria were patients aged 18–65 years, low back-related leg pain with a

corresponding lumbar disc herniation at the relevant side and level confirmed by MRI. The radiologist's written report and the images were evaluated by the treating physician and physiotherapist as part of the clinical evaluation and diagnostic procedure. Exclusion criteria were cauda equina syndrome, ongoing infection, suspected malignancy, pregnancy, breastfeeding, other illness interfering with the study purpose, such as diabetes-neuropathy, inflammatory disease or spinal stenosis, prior surgery at the same disc level or any lumbar fusion, or poor Norwegian language skills. All patients received written information and signed an informed consent form.

Study protocol

Patients underwent a routine clinical examination and evaluation by both a physiotherapist and physician at baseline. At follow-up, patients were re-examined by a physiotherapist, and a physician was consulted if required. All patients received conservative treatment advice. The need for further evaluation by a surgeon was considered by shared decision-making between the patient, physician and physiotherapist, based on duration of leg pain longer than 8–12 weeks and neurological deficits (sensory changes, muscle weakness, or depressed or absent deep tendon reflexes). Final choice of surgery was decided by the patient and a surgeon. Patients completed all questionnaires at baseline and at follow-ups, which were conducted at 6 weeks and 1 year. Only baseline and 6 weeks data were utilized in the present study. All questionnaires were completed after the clinical examination in a separate room or hallway. The patients were instructed to complete the forms on paper, without any involvement from the clinicians, but were given the opportunity to ask for help if needed.

The Norwegian Short-Form McGill Pain Questionnaire-2

The SF-MPQ-2 was translated into Norwegian based on established guidelines for linguistic validation and cross-cultural adaptation for clinical outcome measures¹⁰. We established a workgroup consisting of two consultant physicians (PhDs), a senior physiotherapist (MSc) and two independent forward-translators, one bilingual native speaker of English and one bilingual native speaker of Norwegian. The two forward-translations were compared and discussed in the workgroup and a synthesis of the translations was achieved by consensus. Wording from the Norwegian SF-MPQ⁹ were appraised during the consensus process. A third external translator, bilingual native English speaking, naïve to the questionnaire and prior process, backward translated the questionnaire. The forward and back-translations were then reviewed and consolidated by the workgroup to confirm linguistic equivalence. A pre-final version was tested in 8 patients, who after completing the form were interviewed to evaluate the acceptability and comprehension of the questionnaire. The interview was semi-structured and probed for patients' understanding and interpretation of the questionnaire overall meaning; the instruction-text; each pain descriptor; and the response (numeric rating-scale). Minor changes were implemented and a final Norwegian SF-MPQ-2 (NSF-MPQ-2) was then

completed, following an external proofreading.

Patient-reported outcome measures

Low back pain and leg pain during the last week was assessed using numeric rating scales, with anchors no pain (0) to worst thinkable pain (10).

Neuropathic pain components were assessed using the painDETECT questionnaire¹¹. The questionnaire includes one item about the presence of radiating pain, one item about pain course pattern and seven items on sensory symptoms. Total score ranges from -1 to 38 points.

Anxiety and depression were assessed using the Hopkins Symptom Checklist-25 (HSCL-25)¹², which includes 10 items to assess anxiety and 15 items to assess depression. Each item has four response categories ranging from not at all (1) to extremely (4), referring to symptoms during the previous week. The score is calculated as the mean of the completed items.

Pain related disability was assessed using the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI)^{14,15}. ODI assess 10 areas of pain and daily activities (pain intensity, personal hygiene, lifting, walking, sitting, standing, sleeping, sexual activity, social activity and travelling) with a total score range of 0–100. A higher score indicates greater disability.

Use of pain-related medication was measured by self-reported frequency of use, and is presented here as daily, weekly or monthly/no use. From the questionnaire data, we collapsed the categories monthly and no use, and daily and several times daily.

Statistical analysis

The analyses were based on the COSMIN criteria^{16,17}. NSF-MPQ-2 total score was computed as the mean of all scores. The mean for the subscales continuous pain, intermittent pain, neuropathic pain and affective pain were calculated from the mean score of the descriptors included in each subscale. Descriptive statistics were applied to show the mean, median, range and frequency of descriptor and subscale use.

Content validity was assessed by proportional use of each descriptor. A limit of 33% has been applied as a measure of content validity^{9,18,19} based on the work by Melzack³. Further, to evaluate the potential for missing responses in the lower or upper end of the scale, which may indicate limited content validity²⁰, we examined the percentage of responders that achieved the lowest or highest possible score for the NSF-MPQ-2 total score and the four subscale scores at baseline. A limit of 15% was set as indicating a floor or ceiling effect²⁰.

Construct validity was examined by associations between all the NSF-MPQ-2 scales and

HSCL-25, ODI, painDETECT, leg and back pain intensity. We predefined hypotheses of association based on the construct of the measure. The overall NSF-MPQ-2 and the subscales scores were hypothesized to positively correlate moderately or strongly with ratings of leg pain intensity, painDETECT and ODI. Whereas low to moderate positive correlations were expected between the NSF-MPQ-2 total and subscales scores, and the measures relating to anxiety and depression (HSCL-25) and low back pain.

Responsiveness—longitudinal validity of change—was assessed by determining the associations of the baseline to 6-week change in NSF-MPQ-2 dimensions with the corresponding change in back pain, leg pain and disability (ODI). Based on prior research in a comparable sample²¹ we hypothesized moderate to strong positive correlations with leg pain and disability. Further, we hypothesized a low to moderate positive correlation between the NSF-MPQ-2 dimensions and back pain, which were not the main complaint in the present population. The change scores were calculated as the baseline score subtracted from the 6-week score.

Spearman's rho was used, and coefficients above 0.6 were regarded strong, between 0.6–0.3 moderate, and below 0.3 weak.

Internal consistency reliability was assessed by Cronbach's alpha for the four subscales and total scores. Alpha coefficients between 0.70 and 0.95 was considered acceptable²⁰.

Confirmatory factor analyses were performed to evaluate the validity of the previously identified factor structure in a new language and the present population^{20,22,23}. The data were assessed for uni- and multivariate normality and outliers²⁴. Patients were excluded from subscale analyses if they had 2 or more missing scores on the same subscale. Factor analyses were performed using robust maximum likelihood estimation, with full information maximum likelihood for the missing data²⁵. We pre-specified our main analysis to a fixed four-factor model based on the original work by Dworkin et al.⁴ The 22 descriptors were restricted to load on their designated subscale—i.e. continuous, intermittent, neuropathic or affective. As our results showed high intercorrelations among latent factors, we performed a second-order confirmatory factor analysis in order to evaluate if a global pain construct would account better for all the subscale-constructs²³. The variances were fixed to the latent factors, allowing free estimation of all factor loadings. Acceptability of fit was evaluated based on the absolute index of model fit; root means square error of approximation (RMSEA, recommended value below 0.06) and on the relative index of model fit; comparative fit index (CFI, recommended value close to 0.95)²⁶. All analyses were performed in RStudio v1.0.136²⁷ and R version 3.3.2²⁸, with the package *tidyverse* v1.1.1²⁹, *psych* v1.7.8³⁰, *MVN* v4.0.2³¹, *lavaan* v0.5³² and *semPlot* v1.1³³.

Results

Translation

All phases of the translation received consensus by the workgroup. The backwards translation showed good accordance with the original English version. The patient interviews showed excellent acceptability and comprehension of the NSF-MPQ-2. The original and translated descriptors are presented in the supplementary material, and the questionnaire-form is available through Mapi Research Trust, Lyon, France—<https://eprovide.mapi-trust.org>.

Patient characteristics

Of 90 patients included in the prospective cohort study, 89 returned the questionnaire and were included in the present study (33 females, 56 males). Eighty-six patients completed the questionnaires at the 6-week follow-up. 10 patients had missing responses on the NSF-MPQ-2 (eight patients with 1 missing, two patients with 2 and 3 missing, respectively). One female patient was excluded from analyses concerning the neuropathic subscale due to two missing responses on neuropathic pain descriptors. At the 6-week follow up, 19 (21%) patients (eight female) had received surgical treatment for disc herniation. Patient characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Content validity

Proportion of use per descriptor is shown in Figure 1. Two of the neuropathic subscale descriptors—*cold-freezing pain* and *itching*—were used by less than 33%. Most descriptors were used through the full score range, except *gnawing pain*, *pain caused by light touch* and *itching*, for which no patient scored above 9, 8 and 7 points, respectively. There were no floor or ceiling effects for the total or subscales scores. Seven percent and 10% reported the lowest possible score on the neuropathic and affective subscales, respectively (Table 2).

Construct validity

Regarding construct validity, our hypotheses were generally met. The NSF-MPQ-2 total and subscale scores correlated strongly (ρ above 0.6) with leg pain, except for the neuropathic subscale with a ρ of 0.31. All correlation coefficients between NSF-MPQ-2, ODI and painDETECT were moderate (0.34–0.60), as hypothesized. Moreover, measures of anxiety and depression (HSCL-25) and low back pain were mostly low, with the only moderate correlations between HSCL-25 and NSF-MPQ-2 total and affective score. These results are presented in Table 3.

Our hypothesis of moderate to strong correlations between the change scores of NSF-MPQ-2 with leg pain and disability (ODI) were supported. The change in the continuous and intermittent subscales, as well as the total score, correlated strongly with the change in leg

pain and disability. The change scores in the neuropathic and the affective subscales correlated moderately with the change in these outcomes (Table 4).

Internal consistency reliability

All components of the NSF-MPQ-2 had acceptable reliability as measured by Cronbach's alpha, ranging from 0.70 to 0.79 for the subscales, and 0.88 for the total score. Coefficients and descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2.

Initial data exploration for the confirmatory factor analysis revealed deviations from multivariate normality, and analysis was performed using robust methods. For our main pre-specified four-factor model the overall model fit was found poor, with RMSEA = 0.086, 90% CI (0.067-0.104) and CFI = 0.775. A path diagram with estimates from the factor model is presented in Figure 2. The second-order model fit was similar to the four-factor model, RMSEA = 0.091, 90% CI (0.074-0.107) and CFI = 0.752. The first-order latent factors loaded highly on the second-order latent factor—standardized coefficients at 0.99, 0.68, 0.76 and 0.87 for continuous, intermittent, neuropathic and affective, respectively. In the pre-specified four-factor model the correlations between most of the latent factors were high (0.63-0.83), except between the intermittent and neuropathic subscales (0.36) (Figure 2). Most indicators had factor loadings above 0.4, except for *itching* at 0.261, *cramping pain* at 0.35 and *gnawing pain* at 0.38. The residual correlations, latent factor coefficients and modification indices tables from the four-factor analysis, and a path diagram for the second-order model are available in the supplementary material.

Discussion

In the present study we performed a translation of the SF-MPQ-2 into Norwegian. The final backward translation was in good accordance with the original version. The NSF-MPQ-2 showed excellent acceptability and comprehension during initial testing with patients. The analyses also demonstrated satisfactory content and construct validity, including responsiveness to change, and internal consistency reliability. However, the confirmatory factor analyses raise concerns regarding the previously identified four-factor structure as the overall model fit was relatively poor.

We found correlation coefficients above 0.8 between the continuous and neuropathic, and between the continuous and affective latent factors (Figure 2). Associations above 0.8 are generally considered to indicate poor discriminant validity²³. This may be due to our homogenous patient population, but similar findings were reported by Lovejoy et al.⁷ in patients with a wider range of chronic pain diagnoses. Lovejoy et al. assessed the discriminability of the factor-structure by modelling the loadings of the first-order latent factors (the four subscales structures) on an additional second-order latent global factor. They found that a second-order model with one global latent factor accounted for the different subscale-constructs, with a fit comparable to the 4-factor model. Our second-

order model supports these findings. The high loadings of the four-factors on the second-order latent factor (standardized coefficients from 0.68–0.99) may reflect the presence of a global pain construct accounting for the subscale dimensions. This finding and the high latent factor correlations may indicate that the subscales are not unique, i.e. that they measure the same—or overlapping constructs.

The majority of the indicators were salient in the four-factor model with moderate standardized loadings above 0.4. Three descriptors (*itching*, *cramping pain* and *gnawing pain*) were below this limit, and one may question if they adequately measure their latent constructs in this population²³. This could represent an aetiology-specific effect but gives support for future work exploring descriptor use in the NSF-MPQ-2.

One of the intended key features of the SF-MPQ-2 is to capture elements related to neuropathic pain. In a former study on a subset of the present population, selected only based on being the first enrolled, 88% fulfilled the criteria for definite and 12% fulfilled the criteria for probable neuropathic pain according to the present NeuPSIG grading system^{34,35}. The patients in the present study should therefore to a large extent fulfil the clinical criteria for probable or definite neuropathic pain. However, the neuropathic pain subscale did not stand out in our analyses; the overall factor loading was low; the subscale score and change score had the weakest correlation with leg pain intensity and change in leg pain over time; and two of the six items were used by less than 33% of the subjects. Furthermore, *itching* had the lowest factor loading among all indicators at 0.26 (standardized estimate). Although single descriptors may be specific to certain conditions, the neuropathic subscale generally did not reflect a neuropathic construct well in this population. Our findings are in agreement with Dworkin et al.⁶, who, in a sample of comparable patients, also found poor model fit for the neuropathic latent factor. Our results support the notion that self-report symptom-descriptors may not be sufficiently sensitive or specific to assess neuropathic pain^{34,36,37}. However, symptoms of paraesthesia (*tingling or 'pins and needles'*) and *numbness* were reported by more than 70% of the patients with relatively high loadings in the factor analysis (standardized estimates above 0.65). Paraesthesia and numbness have previously been found severely bothersome by patients with low back-related leg pain³⁸. As these descriptors were not included in the first SF-MPQ, we suggest using the SF-MPQ-2 for patients with low back-related leg pain.

The present work is limited by the sample population and size. Further, some caution is needed in interpretation of the confirmatory factor analysis, based on the unsatisfactory fit of the pre-specified model²³. As the rate of non-response on the SF-MPQ-2 was low, missing is an unlikely cause of bias in the present study. All patients were referred from primary to secondary health care and may not be representative of the average patient with low back-related leg pain, resulting in limitations regarding external validity. However, patient characteristics are comparable to previous studies on patients with low back-related leg pain in secondary health care^{39,40}. Further, all patients were consecutively included through regular referral routines, and not through advertising or other channels.

Thus, we believe the potential for selection bias due to the process of recruitment was low.

Conclusion

The present cross-cultural adaptation of the Norwegian version of the SF-MPQ-2 showed excellent acceptability and comprehension. We found satisfactory content and construct validity, including responsiveness to change, and internal consistency reliability. However, our confirmatory factor analysis raised concerns regarding the factor-structure. Until more evidence emerges for the four-factor solution we suggest the Norwegian SF-MPQ-2 should be used as a single measure.

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Figures

Figure 1. Statistics for NSF-MPQ-2 pain descriptors. Boxplot shows median; interquartile range; largest value no further than 1.5 × interquartile range; and outliers. Barplot shows proportion of subjects who used each pain descriptor. The red vertical line indicates the pre-specified 33% content validity limit. The figure does not show the order of descriptors used in the questionnaire, but are rearranged to show the performance of each respective subscale, namely the continuous, intermittent, neuropathic or affective.

Norwegian SF-MPQ-2

Figure 2. Path diagram with standardized estimates for the NSF-MPQ-2 confirmatory factor analysis. The variances were fixed to the latent factors, allowing free estimation of all factor loadings. Numbers represent (left to right); variances, factor loadings and latent factor-correlations.

Tables

Table 1. Patient characteristics

	Baseline (N=89)	6 weeks (N=86)
Age, years	42.3 (9.5)	
Females, <i>n</i> (%)	33 (37%)	
Duration leg pain (weeks), median (IQR)	11 (6-22)	
Pain medication, <i>n</i> (%)		
Daily	65 (73%)	34 (39%)
Weekly	11 (12%)	11 (13%)
Monthly or no use	13 (15%)	41 (48%)
Norwegian SF-MPQ-2	3.4 (1.7)	1.7 (1.8)
Continuous	3.9 (2.0)	2.0 (2.0)
Intermittent	4.0 (2.2)	2.0 (2.3)
Neuropathic	2.4 (1.8)	1.4 (1.7)
Affective	3.2 (2.5)	1.4 (2.1)
Pain intensity (0-10)		
Low back pain	5.0 (2.9)	3.0 (2.9)
Leg pain	6.9 (2.0)	3.9 (3.2)
Anxiety and depression (HSCL-25*) (0-4)	1.48 (0.4)	1.34 (0.4)
Oswestry disability index (0-100)	42.7 (16.7)	24.4 (18.4)
painDETECT Questionnaire (-1-38)	13.3 (5.5)	8.7 (6.7)

Values are mean (SD) if not otherwise stated.

* Hopkins symptom checklist-25

Table 2. Descriptives for NSF-MPQ-2 with internal consistency reliability statistics (N=89).

	Score			Floor/Ceiling*	Skew	Std.error	Coefficient α
	Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)	Min-max				
NSF-MPQ-2 total	3.4 (1.7)	3.3 (2.0–4.7)	0.5–8	0/0	0.44	0.18	0.88
Continuous	3.9 (2.0)	3.8 (2.5–5.3)	0–8.5	2/0	0.11	0.21	0.73
Intermittent	4.0 (2.2)	3.7 (2.3–5.8)	0–9.7	2/0	0.31	0.24	0.77
Neuropathic	2.4 (1.8)	2.3 (1.0–3.5)	0–7.8	7/0	0.60	0.19	0.70
Affective	3.2 (2.5)	2.8 (1.3–4.5)	0–10	10/1	0.75	0.26	0.79

* Floor and ceiling effects were assessed by examining the percentage of responders that achieved the lowest or highest possible score. A limit of 15% was set as indicating a floor or ceiling effect.

Table 3. Correlation coefficients between measures to assess construct validity.

	Norwegian Short-Form McGill Pain Questionnaire					HSCL-25	ODI	PDQ	Leg pain
	Total score	Continuous	Intermittent	Neuropathic	Affective				
Continuous	0.85								
Intermittent	0.79	0.52							
Neuropathic	0.71	0.58	0.32						
Affective	0.79	0.61	0.54	0.46					
HSCL-25	0.36	0.25	0.27	0.21	0.36				
ODI	0.60	0.51	0.49	0.34	0.55	0.47			
PDQ	0.58	0.46	0.36	0.73	0.42	0.22	0.40		
Leg pain	0.70	0.65	0.62	0.31	0.60	0.25	0.63	0.34	
Back pain	0.22	0.15	0.22	0.18	0.22	0.09	0.24	0.32	0.35

Correlations computed using Spearman's rho.

Table 4. Correlation coefficients between the measures' change-scores* to assess longitudinal validity/responsiveness.

	Norwegian Short-Form McGill Pain Questionnaire						Leg pain	Back pain
	Total score	Continuous	Intermittent	Neuropathic	Affective			
Continuous	0.86							
Intermittent	0.79	0.60						
Neuropathic	0.72	0.54	0.39					
Affective	0.80	0.64	0.48	0.54				
Leg pain	0.64	0.62	0.59	0.32	0.48			
Back pain	0.38	0.35	0.38	0.23	0.28	0.61		
ODI	0.65	0.61	0.65	0.37	0.48	0.74	0.50	

Correlations computed using Spearman's rho.

* Baseline score subtracted from the 6-week score.